

Editorial

Modelling—International Open Access Journal of Modelling in Engineering Science

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Modelling in engineering science embraces a wide area of theoretical results, methodological aspects and practical findings, with particular regard to computer-based modelling approaches. This paradigm is now of renewed interest specially thanks to the emerging big data setting, which opens the door to a very wide family of application scenarios that range from natural phenomena modelling to scientific computing, from complex dynamic systems (e.g., communication networks, pandemic epidemics, demographic evolutions, and so forth) to modern cyber-physical systems, from intelligent transportation systems to smart cities and bio-medical systems, and many others.

Modelling in engineering science encompasses a broad collection of models, techniques, algorithms and methodologies for representing, managing and implementing modelling systems and tools with an astonishing impact on science, technology and society. In such a scientific environment, numerous achievements, advancements and findings are expected to be pursued and explored, by proposing innovative scientific results as well as solid engineering realizations. Therefore, modelling of real-life phenomena (both natural and artificial) will stimulate the birth of a novel computer science discipline focused on complex systems, systems integration methodologies and paradigms, and computational intelligence tools.

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Conflicts of Interest: The author declares no conflict of interest.

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